

Zenodo catch-all repository

Instructions to upload EcoStack research outputs to Zenodo

Step 1

- Log-in to Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/>
- If **not** existing user, suggested option is to log-in with or ORCID.
- Otherwise, sign-up with email

Step 2

- Click on Upload button (fig. 1.)

Fig. 1.

Step 3

- Click on Upload button for new upload
- 3 stages for upload process
 - Upload minimum one file **or** fill-in required fields (marked with a red star).
 - Press "**Save**" to save your upload for editing later.
 - When ready, press "**Publish**" to finalize and make your upload public.
- Complete all required information (Upload type, Basic information and License)
 - If a **DOI** has already been assigned, can enter this otherwise, Zenodo will register a new DOI (fig. 2).
 - Access rights should be specified as **Open Access** (fig. 3)
- All outputs (publications, videos, data etc.) from EcoStack projects **must have funding information given.**
 - Specify: European Commission (EU) and **EcoStack or 773554** to identify upload as part of EcoStack project (fig. 3).
- Completing other information fields are optional

Fig. 2

Basic information required ▾

Digital Object Identifier

Optional. Did your publisher already assign a DOI to your upload? If not, leave the field empty and we will register a new DOI for you. A DOI allows others to easily and unambiguously cite your upload. Please note that it is NOT possible to edit a Zenodo DOI once it has been registered by us, while it is always possible to edit a custom DOI.

Publication date *

Required. Format: YYYY-MM-DD. In case your upload was already published elsewhere, please use the date of first publication.

Title *

Required.

Authors *

Optional.

[+ Add another author](#)

Description *

Required.

Version

Optional. Mostly relevant for software and dataset uploads. Any string will be accepted, but semantically-versioned tag is recommended. See [semver.org](#) for more information on semantic versioning.

Language

Optional. Primary language of the record. Start by typing the language's common name in English, or its ISO 639 code (two or three-letter code). See [ISO 639 language codes list](#) for more information.

Keywords

[+ Add another keyword](#)

Additional notes

Optional.

Fig. 3

License required ▾

Access right *

Open Access

Embargoed Access

Restricted Access

Closed Access

Required. Open access uploads have considerably higher visibility on Zenodo.

License *

Required. Selected license applies to all of your files displayed on the top of the form. If you want to upload some of your files under different licenses, please do so in separate uploads. If you cannot find the license you're looking for, include a relevant LICENSE file in your record and choose one of the *Other* licenses available (*Other (Open)*, *Other (Attribution)*, etc.). The supported licenses in the list are harvested from opendefinition.org and spdx.org. If you think that a license is missing from the list, please [contact us](#).

Funding recommended ▾

Zenodo is integrated into reporting lines for research funded by the European Commission via [OpenAIRE](#). Specify grants which have funded your research, and we will let your funding agency know!

Grants

Optional. OpenAIRE-supported projects only. For other funding acknowledgements, please use the *Additional Notes* field.
Note: a human Zenodo curator will need to validate your upload - you may experience a delay before it is available in OpenAIRE.

[+ Add another grant](#)

Related/alternate identifiers recommended >

Contributors optional >

References optional >

Journal optional >

Conference optional >

Book/Report/Chapter optional >

Thesis optional >

Subjects optional >